

117) and RD19 attained maximum height with medium deep water. The main tiller usually was taller than the primary secondary tillers.

The number of internodes was generally similar in shallow and medium deep water and considerably higher in deep water (see table) although height in

medium deep water was 10-40% more than that in shallow water. Height was not strongly related to the number of internodes, but was to elongation. In deep water, the upper internodes were longest in all but one line. In RD19 and progeny no. 42, the second internode was longest.

In shallow and medium deep water, the second internode from the top was the longest in half the lines (see table). The contribution of longest internode to the final height varied from 26 to 61%. That the top three internodes elongated more than the rest should be considered in further studies. *ℒ*

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Tungro (RTV) spread in rice fields

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We studied the spread of RTV in

transplanted aman season by transplanting 21-d-old susceptible Purbachi seedlings in 10- × 10-m plots. The center 2- × 2-m of each plot was planted with RTV-inoculated seedlings. Number and position of RTV-infected plants were recorded 5 times at weekly

Tungro dispersal in rice fields, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Direction	Distance (range in m)	Infected plants ^a (%)				
		21 DT	28 DT	35 DT	43 DT	50 DT
East	0-1	1	0	0	6	33
	1-2	0	0	0	4	24
	2-3	0	1	1	7	22
	3-4	0	0	0	7	19
West	0-1	2	1	0	15	24
	1-2	0	0	0	9	32
	2-3	0	0	0	8	27
	3-4	0	0	1	6	30
North	0-1	0	1	1	14	21
	1-2	1	0	2	5	31
	2-3	1	0	0	7	28
	3-4	0	0	1	3	21
South	0-1	1	1	0	15	31
	1-2	1	1	0	9	23
	2-3	0	1	0	3	21
	3-4	0	0	0	5	11
Northeast	0 -1.4	0	0	0	11	36
	1.4-2.8	0	0	0	2	32
	2.8-4.2	0	1	0	4	18
	4.2-5.7	0	0	0	6	19
Northwest	0 -1.4	4	0	0	6	40
	1.4-2.8	0	0	0	12	23
	2.8-4.2	0	1	1	8	29
	4.2-5.7	0	2	1	10	24
Southeast	0 -1.4	0	1	0	6	26
	1.4-2.8	0	0	0	6	22
	2.8-4.2	0	0	1	3	13
	4.2-5.7	0	0	0	4	5
Southwest	0 -1.4	0	1	0	10	33
	1.4-2.8	0	0	0	10	23
	2.8-4.2	0	1	0	3	18
	4.2-5.1	0	0	0	2	16

^a Mean of 2 replications. Percentage infected plants in 2-m² plots east, west, north, and south of the center plot; and in 1-m² plots northeast, northwest, southeast, and southwest of the center plot.

intervals, beginning 21 d after transplanting (DT). Disease spread was recorded by time, direction, and distance from the center plot.

RTV spread was positively correlated with wind direction. The rate of dispersal was slow before 35 DT and high at 50 DT. Percentage of infected plants was highest within 1 m of the center plot (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of planting time on stem rot (SR) incidence

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Four years of insect pest surveys in Haryana indicate that SR is a serious constraint to rice production. It is most common in Kurukshetra, Kamal, and Ambala districts, where all the cultivated varieties are affected.

We studied the effect of planting time on SR incidence in 1984 at HAURRS. One-month-old Jaya, Jhona 349, Pusa 33, Basmati 370, HAU 118-110, and HAU 2313-39 seedlings were planted in 2.5-m² infected plots on 18 Jul, 3 Aug, and 18 Aug at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications and disease incidence was determined by the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

The Jul planting had highest SR incidence, perhaps because of high (28°C) temperatures and relative humidity (81%) prevailing during the susceptible stage of the crop. Disease incidence in all the